

IMPROVING SOCIAL MANAGEMENT IN A NEW SOCIETY

Rakhimjonova Gulzira

Master of the 1st stage of the Department
of Sociology of the National University of Uzbekistan.

e-mail: raximjonovagulzira@gmail.com

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Abstract. *An analysis of modern social management experience shows that all key functions of social management depend on the development of the social system, and their content and role change. This article examines the improvement of social management in modern society. Key functions are identified, categorized by characteristics: those that ensure favorable conditions for the development of entities, and those that organize and systematize social associations. The relationship between management and self-organization in small businesses is analyzed, as well as the effectiveness of social management in military academies. It is concluded that the management process often conflicts with self-organization and requires reform and an individualized approach.*

Keywords: *social management, society, small business, small entrepreneurship, social technologies, military education, social theory.*

The social sphere acts as one of the fundamental subsystems of society, as the state of its sectors significantly, and sometimes decisively, affects each individual, determines quality of life, and creates “human capital” – an educated and healthy nation. Ultimately, it is this type of capital that makes a decisive contribution to the country's economic development. But the external impact of social sectors is not limited to increasing the population's capacity as a workforce. It also includes a social component – the opportunity for individual self-realization.

The main entities governing the region's social sphere are state authorities and public self-government bodies. Speaking about the system of state governance in the social sphere, it can be noted that it has changed little over many decades.

Meanwhile, improving organizational structures is one of the priority areas of reforming the social sector management system. This will strengthen the fractured vertical management structure and consolidate financial, material, and human resources, which is particularly important in the context of decentralized governance and funding shortages.

Social management functions are the areas of managerial influence on the relationships and relations of people. Their implementation should ensure the desired response of the object and a certain change in its state [1].

Social management functions can be divided into three groups. The first group is responsible for ensuring favorable conditions and their gradual improvement. These include:

- creating a safe environment;
- assisting people in obtaining resources, creating opportunities for increasing well-being;
- protecting health and labor, and improving the level of their conditions;
- creating opportunities for individual participation in the management of various social institutions.

The second group is organizational in nature:

- influencing professional and cultural development;
- influencing social values and ethics;
- ensuring social discipline;
- increasing the level of social activity.

The third group of functions systematizes social associations:

- interacting social groups;
- effective social structures;
- creative social institutions.

Social management influences social objects by:

- formulating and setting management goals, developing ways to achieve them;
- developing and streamlining organizational structures to implement social management plans and goals;
- ensuring coordination of actions in the process of achieving goals;
- motivating people to perform certain actions;
- empowering people with certain skills and knowledge;
- monitoring compliance with established standards and rules.

An analysis of modern social management practices shows that all key functions of social management depend on the development of the social system, changing their content and role. For example, the activities of a commercial enterprise include the following stages: organization, production, and achievement of results.

Each can be a separate object of management [2]. The military education system shapes behavioral patterns and traditions that remain relevant over time [3].

In fulfilling the function of reproducing officer cadres, military training centers, on the one hand, train regular officers for the Armed Forces, and on the other, they train the mobilization reserve of military personnel discharged from the Armed Forces upon completion of their contracts.

Furthermore, graduates of military training centers receive a national diploma, which allows them to find employment with a civilian company [4].

Social management in modern society impacts organizations (commercial, non-profit, formal, and informal) and individuals. To improve the effectiveness of social management functions in the external environment of small businesses, methods are being developed and refined at the global, federal, and organizational levels. To achieve effective impact at all levels, it is important to consider economic, political, and cultural factors.

Research results and current social management practices demonstrate that the primary areas of activity in addressing these challenges must be focused on organizational, technical, and scientific areas. Social management of the internal sphere of entrepreneurship is carried out within the following subsystems: organizational, personnel, production, financial and economic, and information [5].

Thus, the main obstacle to the planned development of the social sector lies not so much in the lack of financial resources as in the absence of an effective management system.

Underestimating the management factor has repeatedly led to negative social consequences and distortions of regional society. The lack of practical theories of social management hinders the development of regional markets for social services [6].

The above suggests that attention must now be focused on the fundamental problem at the core of modern social policy: the methodological issues of developing flexible (innovative) regional management systems. It should be noted that the main directions of social development for both the state and the region may be the same, but the organizational, legal, and economic mechanisms must be specific to each state and region [7].

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